

Occlusion therapy in positional defects of an eye. Is it still state of the art?

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Abstract

Strabismus and heterophoria are important health issues in primary care. Involvement of an experienced ophthalmologist is essential, but so is primary care, especially to ensure adequate compliance with a treatment that is associated with significant impact on "how patients look." Primary care physicians share responsibility for ensuring compliance with occlusion, particularly in adolescents treated with long-term occlusion therapy. We also discuss the use of self-adhesive patches with alternatives that cause less stress to the skin.

Primary care aspects of occlusion therapy

Positional defects of the eyes beyond the 120th day of life are more than a cosmetic problem. If parents notice that their child is squinting, there is no way around an ophthalmologist. Occlusion of the healthy eye can then at least halt and sometimes prevent loss of vision in the squinting eye. The strabismus itself can sometimes only be corrected by surgery.^{1,3,8} We have reviewed the relevant literature and are concerned that children with congenital strabismus are not treated as early as possible today, because the occlusion patch has apparently become a stigma.^{1,3,5} Thus, there is a danger of an increase in amblyopia. This is because, in order to avoid disturbing double images, the child's brain suppresses the visual impression of the squinting eye. As a result, this eye becomes significantly weak-sighted and no glasses will help. Should the healthy eye later become diseased, the squint eye offers little reserve. In addition, many professions require good, three-dimensional vision.^{1,3} Reasons enough to take countermeasures at an early stage. In order for the vision in the deviating eye to develop as well as possible, the healthy eye is closed - after any existing defective vision has been compensated for with suitable glasses - in order to train the squinting eye and to 'force' the brain to 'see' with the weak eye. The measurement for the glasses should be done by an ophthalmologist because of the mandatory cycloplegia. Only this may paralyze the ciliary muscle by drops, in order to determine, independently of the accommodation, the actual refraction. One should refrain from a hasty use of prism lenses. These can be useful in individual cases, but can also have a negative effect and result in the need for strabismus surgery.⁶⁻⁸ Furthermore, occlusion therapy should not only be maintained until the patient is 12 years old, as is common today, but until the patient has fully grown, i.e. until the patient is 18 or even 21 years old.^{2,4,5,7} Compliance is a considerable problem here, also because children with taped eyes and glasses initially see less good. An important aspect is also the skin damage that can be caused by adhesive plaster material (Fig 2). To protect the skin from damage during prolonged occlusion therapy, covers made of non-adhesive materials (Fig. 3) should be used instead of plasters. In case of a dermatitis due to adhesives patches a soft fabric cover can be worn until the skin is back to normal.

Fig. 1
Classic eye-patch in a child
Self-adhesive plasters damage the skin

Fig. 2
Eczema/dermatitis
Endangers patient's compliance

Fig. 3
Skin friendly eye cover
To be worn permanently

Fig. 4
Healing fabric during eczema
To be worn temporarily

The chances of success for improvement or much more successful later strabismus surgery increase with patience and sufficiently long conservative therapy. When the affected eye sees better, this reduces its tendency to gradually deviate again postoperatively because it has been actively involved in vision. Early surgery can even restore spatial vision. However, it should not be forgotten that after early surgery, there is a risk that a second revision surgery may become necessary. As a rule, surgery - if it is chosen as a route - is performed between the second year of life and puberty, mainly for aesthetic and psychosocial reasons.²⁻⁷

Conclusion

It seems crucial that strabismus therapy is consistently followed well into the second decade and the use of non-adhesive patches instead of the often used adhesive patches, even if surgery has already been performed. Although the medical industry is constantly introducing new self-adhesive eye patches to the market, often with age-appropriate imprints, it is obvious that having an adhesive patch on the skin for years is not healthy for the skin. Severe eczema can be the result. Therefore, classical models should be used, especially if long-term therapy is planned. In summary, we conclude that long-term occlusion therapy is still state of the art, especially in combination with surgery whenever a positive outcome is likely. Primary care providers play an important role in ensuring compliance, especially in adolescent patients.

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Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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